

Study of the Gender Perspective in STEM degrees

Sample size: 138

Average age:

20,51

Academic year:

Pre-degree studies:

Current job:

Degree that you are enrolled in: ▾

Age:

Context

FEMALE

MALE

Degree that you are enrolled in: ▾

Computer science

Age:

FEMALE

MALE

Degree that you are enrolled in: ▾

Age:

Integration

FEMALE

MALE

Degree that you are enrolled in: ▾

Age:

Teamwork

FEMALE

MALE

Degree that you are enrolled in: ▾

Academic results

Age:

FEMALE

Average grade: **6,34**

Average grade (in subjects related to computer science): **6,16**

MALE

Average grade: **6,6**

Average grade (in subjects related to computer science): **6,85**

Degree that you are enrolled in: ▾

Future outlook

Age:

FEMALE

MALE

Do you plan to do enroll another degree?

Do you plan to do enroll another degree?

Do you plan to enroll a master's degree?

Do you plan to enroll a master's degree?

Do you plan to enroll a PhD program?

Do you plan to enroll a PhD program?

Degree that you are enrolled in: ▾

Gender perspective

Age:

FEMALE

MALE

Why do you think there is a greater presence of men than women in STEM degrees?

Degree that you are enrolled in:

Age:

FEMALE

MALE

Why do you think there is a greater presence of men than women in STEM degrees? ▾

1. prejudices of the past
2. no idea the truth
3. couldn't say, I think it's more a matter of taste.
4. by prejudice
5. because women are made to believe that they are less intelligent in technical subjects
6. because science has always been associated with men.
7. Yes
8. Well I do not know, really. Perhaps because in society it is not so seen that there are women working in this type of position.
9. There are more and more women, but they still continue to see themselves as men's careers and that they are better at it
10. Men tend to like things related to computers more
11. I think it's more about taste (most of my friends don't like computer science at all).
12. I don't know... could it be a coincidence? My first career also had a disproportionate number of women, and it was a scientific career.
13. Historically, it has been promoted that men be in this type of career, while women went to other "easier" ones or those related to caring for people.
14. From personal experience there are very few of us and that makes the environment less pleasant so to speak. If establishing relationships is already difficult in engineering since there is a lot of pressure and little free time, when there isn't even a woman it becomes more uphill. On the other hand, there is always a bad experience. In my first year of college I suffered harassment from some students and even a teacher (who had to publicly apologize in class). In the end, being a woman in this career becomes complicated and many abandon or do not choose this option.
15. Depending on your education and tastes, for example, before, boys were offered more to play with building games and girls were offered more caring games, depending on what you play and have fun with, it will be what you want to dedicate yourself to.
16. By taste
17. Because there are few women, and it is difficult to make friends, apart from the fact that they can underestimate you for being a woman.
18. Because the whole society is telling you all the time that it is not your place. Even the toilets of the Polytechnic School I for men are larger, while those for aunts are one per floor. As if to tell you that there is only one room in this place. And the worst thing is that this type of thing seems like bullshit or an exaggeration to men and it's frustrating!
19. Because technical careers have never been focused on women

Why do you think there is a greater presence of men than women in STEM degrees? ▾

1. think this is due to the great participation of men in IT as such. Boys also spend more time on the computer than girls on average.
2. think it is related to the fact that men manage pressure more at times.
3. simple tastes
4. own choice
5. matter of taste
6. just because
7. interests
8. for human stupidity
9. by stereotypes
10. a matter of each person's taste, just as there are fewer men in other careers
11. Women tend more toward careers that are more customer-friendly, such as healthcare or teaching.
12. Women are not so interested
13. Why yes, no one prevents anyone from getting into a career or studying what they like, generally
14. Tradition
15. They just don't care
16. These careers are seen as being only for men, since it is more common to see in everyday life or in movies and series a man being the computer hacker on duty. And the reality is not that.
17. The prejudices
18. Tastes
19. Stereotypes, low representation of women, structural barriers
20. Stereotypes on the one hand and prejudices towards engineering students on the other. The difficulty of the career also influences the decision of both male and female students, but I suppose that students of the opposite gender already have another vocation in mind.
21. Some percentage will not want to, I suppose, just as I would not like to study teaching.
22. Society does not normalize the presence of women in these careers (e.g. the typical computer scientist in movies is almost always a man)

OTHER GENDRES

Why do you think there is a greater presence of men than women in STEM degrees? ▾

1. believe that this is something that has to do with society, women and men are taught differently and women are predisposed to choose careers more focused on caring for people. Furthermore, within the family environment this happens in the same way, a differentiation is made between careers supposedly focused on men and women and this causes family members to advise sons and daughters differently regarding their career choices.
2. Due to social conditioning, although women are not directly told "you can't study technical careers", before they were told and now that thought remains in some parts of society and it is rare to see women in that type of work.
3. Because the careers in which you "help people" such as teaching, social work, psychology are better presented to women than technical careers which are presented better to men.
4. Because of the traditional belief that women are better off raising children, caring for families and doing housework.

How do you think the presence of women in these degrees could be increased?

Degree that you are enrolled in: ▼

Age:

FEMALE

MALE

How do you think the presence of women in these degrees could be increased? ▼

1. treating everyone as people and valuing their intellectual qualities regardless of their gender
2. giving courses and facilities to girls who are in their primary and secondary studies to encourage them to discover the large number of options that exist and not to be guided by prejudices
3. Trying to eliminate those prejudices that you have
4. The first thing is that it is not necessary to force it, that is, there does not need to be an equal number of men and women in all places. It's more about informing both genders equally. Stop marketing kitchen toys for girls and construction toys for boys. If we treated both equally and guided girls with the different options available, careers in engineering would be considered from a young age.
5. That there is advertising in which women are also the main character, linked to science in children's toys
6. Start seeing us as possible people in that area, instead of women in that area. You know I don't want to feel like that 29%. I don't think the problem is the cut-off mark or the lack of accessibility, the percentage of women in medicine is 68.7% and the cut-off mark is 11 to 13 out of 14. The problem is not accessibility.
7. Speaking more about the high need for computer scientists in the labor market. I had never considered this career until I was asked to participate in the I want to be an engineer activity.
8. Seeing examples of female engineers
9. Providing interesting games for children and adolescents with talks, videos and video games that are related to the tastes of the majority of women.
10. Promoting this type of work
11. Perhaps giving visibility in engineering career institutes, giving talks and showing that, at least computing, is not just video games.
12. Motivating girls from a young age to be interested in science and not only associate them with care careers such as medicine or nursing. Also, in turn, teach children that they do not have to dedicate themselves to science or numbers to be more "valid".
13. Make them understand that both men and women will be good at careers of this type, engineering...
14. It's like the whiting that bites its tail, there will be more women when there are more women studying the race. I believe that little by little the female presence will become bigger, it's a matter of waiting.
15. Introducing them from a young age to hobbies such as those of boys, video games, programming, etc.
16. Increasing the visibility of women who work in these fields (which are not few).
17. I think it is something that should be normalized, not pointing out the number of women

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How do you think the presence of women in these degrees could be increased? ▼

1. think that little by little and with time those social customs that we have been carrying for years will change, so I don't know if something specific should be done, perhaps a little more visibility or publicity.
2. think that giving talks and informing more about technical careers
3. promoting data and encouraging them to see that it is not just for men
4. not influence each person's personal tastes so much and let them do what they want from a young age
5. leaving freedom to do what they want, but without imposing it
6. improving the environment and breaking down stigmas
7. can't force anyone to study something they don't want to. Women can study in any career and the problem is not the lack of inclusion of the female gender in women's careers.
8. You don't have to increase, you always try to equalize things but not everything works that way in my opinion, if more men like computer engineering that's what it is.
9. Working on aspects from a young age, if computer science is made known from a younger age it would be discovered by the entire public, and it would be easier for women to become interested in more technical careers.
10. Women are free to pursue the career they want; if they are not interested in entering more technical careers, they are as free to do so as they are to enter careers where the female sex predominates. Is there this same questionnaire for those careers that seek to interest men more?
11. Without putting pressure on people, since just as there are races with many more women than men, there can be races with many more men than women. Therefore I do not understand the meaning of this question, everyone can study what they want. And regarding the following questions, I find it embarrassing that they try to get more people to access a career just because other people want to. Each one who earns their own by demonstrating their worth through their own merits, studying because they like it and not because they are paid to study in a field they don't like.
12. With the presence of women in senior positions or their greater participation in high-impact projects. I don't know, can something really be done definitively to solve the stupidity, lack of empathy and discrimination based on gender or race? In my opinion, I think it is about carrying out small acts like this survey.
13. Why exactly would you want to do that? Nobody pressures anyone to choose one career or another and even less so based on gender, at least I think so.
14. Trying to change a little the view that these types of careers are intended only for men.
15. Treating everyone equally, without undervaluing people because of their sex
16. Through programs that promote computer learning, and through the teaching of computer science in Primary, ESO and Baccalaureate.
17. There should be no gender distinction in terms of the tastes of children and young people,

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OTHER GENDRES

How do you think the presence of women in these degrees could be increased? ▼

1. Promoting the orientation of students in institutes and leaving behind the differentiation of careers by gender, seeking only that people choose a career that they like and that adapts to them, their preferences and their knowledge. In addition, it would also include guidance in the family environment to create a consensus between the institute, the student and the families.
2. In my institute, for example, they gave talks and works about women with great importance in this type of field, in my opinion it helps to increase the visibility that it is not something rare (talks, posters...)
3. Fostering a less technical and more artistic vision of the career. That is to say, do not present engineering as something that is only physics, programming or mathematics. Presenting it as a good method to exploit people's creativity and ingenuity.
4. null

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